

Integrating Cloth-Link Antenna and Machine Learning for Enhancing Antenna Parameters for Biomedical Application

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Abstract – The purpose of this research is to discover new methods for monitoring and detecting biomedical applications using a microstrip patch antenna with a circular patch and defected ground structure. Antenna that is affordable, lightweight, small, and simple to fabricate. The antenna is infused into a denim material whose loss tangent is 0.04 and dielectric constant is 2.2, which is operated at an Ultra – Wideband (UWB) frequency varying from 3.36 GHz - 14.16 GHz. The proposed system is further analysed by Machine Learning algorithm – Genetic Algorithm to enhance the gain, bandwidth, directivity and many other parameters of the antenna. In the world of biomedicine, this technology can greatly advance treatment plans and patient care.

Keywords – Biomedical, Denim material, Machine Learning - Genetic Algorithm, Microstrip Patch Antenna, UWB frequency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the last couple of years, the merger of wearable technology with our daily staple outfits has been a rise and a good number of people find this technology convenient and useful. However, the soaring appeal for effortless communication and uninterrupted connectivity this requires the development of UWB (Ultra – Wide Band) antenna that can be indirectly worn in clothing to reside in the research arena perceiving tremendous buzz. With regards to healthcare, semiconductor sensors are capable of measuring physiological data, including blood pressure, glucose level, temperature, weight and heartbeats, moreover, it can equip microwave imagining and biomedical imagining within the x band. Our investigation method proposes building UWB variable conformal antenna with core material - denim. However, we aim eventually to enable the design and manufacturing of stylish and effective antennas that go beyond the restrictions of the common antenna substrates by taking advantages of the exceptional characteristics of denim material, consisting of its flexibility, durability, and aesthetic appeal, to name a few. Deemed as a simple methodical design procedure which includes simulation, it enhances the feasibility and practicality of meeting the existing demand, high performing antennas on wearable devices which are made from denim. The bulk density, moisture content, fabric components, structure, and operation frequency all effect the relative dielectric constant and $\tan \sigma$ loss of these different fabric materials such as cotton, denim, silk, or wool whose $\tan \sigma$ loss value extends from 1.04 to 1.9.

Partly, based on the Genetic Algorithms (GA), they have been showing themselves as useful optimisation tools in the antenna design. The structures of GA were elicited by the principles of natural selection and genetics. Therefore, GA is capacitated to refine and evolve, generating antennas that perform with optimum features.

We begin a process to form a connection or interaction between optimal UWB antennas and genetic algorithms. The aim of our research is cross examination of the optimization possibilities of genetic algorithms with radio wave antennas design for the purpose to improve their bandwidth, gain, directivity, and VSWR. Applying UWB transmission features and high efficiency of Genetic algorithms approach is our target. We try to develop new products that will solve complex problems of antenna system designing.

II. ANTENNA STRUCTURE AND DESIGN

A Microstrip antenna proposed in this paper, for Ultra-Wideband applications, is based on a substrate made of denim cloth. The radiation patch on the antenna is intended to be circular in shape and possessing a combination of a central square slot and two elliptical slots with a rectangular microstrip feed line and a ground which includes intentional defects in it. Whole presented antenna is a circular patch incorporating a slot of rectangular shape in the middle, using its resonance characteristics tuning it for ultra-wideband operating frequency bands. The size of dielectric substrate is $20 \times 30 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$, the impedance matching (all the studies have led to the creation that for the antenna feed that the HFSS uses, a 50Ω microstrip feeder).

Fig 1. Top View of the antenna

Fig 2. Bottom View of the antenna

Denim is the substrate material utilized, and its value for the loss tangent is 0.04 and its dielectric constant is 2.2. The antenna proposed is working at an operating frequency of 8 GHz and the antenna's operating bandwidth, which spans from 3.36 GHz to 14.16 GHz, satisfies UWB communication standards. The suggested antenna's top and bottom views are seen in the Fig 1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE I
PARAMETER SIZES OF THE ANTENNA

Parameter	Size(mm)
L	30
W	20
L1	13
W1	3.5
L2	5.5
W2	7
L3	10
W3	20
L4	6.5
W4	3.5
R	8.8
A	1.5
B	0.5
Thickness	1

Originally, a single element is proposed but later on we have increased the number of elements in the design. We have created antenna arrays with two and four elements. These designs will improve the gain, the directivity, the bandwidth and VSWR of the antenna. In two - element antenna array the antennas are positioned opposite to each other and in four - element antenna array the antennas are placed orthogonally to each other. Fig 3 and 4 shows the suggested antenna array designs with two and four elements respectively.

Fig 3. Design of two - elements antenna array

Fig 4. Design of four - elements antenna array

III. GENETIC ALGORITHM IN SUGGESTED ANTENNA DESIGN

GA is generally considered as an evolutionary algorithm, which derives its search behaviour from the principles of genetics and natural selection. GA were first introduced by John Holland in the sixties and are commonly used to tackle various difficult travel and optimization problems.

It is possible to increase yield because of the antenna design level and how applying genetic algorithm affects overall performance. However, the antenna design process requires to find the appropriate sets of elements such as sizes, shapes, and the ones used as materials. These are utilized to obtain results such as good gain, bandwidth and directivity. We have thought about how long the slot would be on the suggested antenna patch. We gave the initial size of the slot as 5.5 mm. We implemented the GA on MATLAB R2020 platform. An overview of the use of genetic algorithm to improve gain, bandwidth and directivity in antenna design is provided below:

A. Representation of Solutions:

A set of parameters that specify the geometry and characteristics of an antenna can be used to describe a solution in the context of antenna design. The antenna's length, width, height, material composition, and other pertinent variables like slots dimensions of the proposed antenna are the examples of these parameters.

B. Initialisation:

Either a random process or a heuristic approach is used to create the initial population of feasible antenna designs. Every member of the population is an individual antenna configuration.

C. Fitness Function:

To assess the performance of every antenna in the population, a fitness function is defined. The fitness function for gain improvement should be created with the antenna's gain in mind, taking impedance matching, radiation pattern, and directivity into account.

D. Selection:

The health of the population members is measured by a fitness index. The ones who have the highest score are elected for reproduction. An individual with higher scores is more preferred to this group.

These then provided configurations whose gain trails were more pronounced, which mimicked the process of natural selection.

E. Crossover:

Individuals to help develop new models are selected by combing their genetic data. The two parent antennas in the context of antenna design could be altered for example by switching given settings or certain portions of antenna designs.

F. Mutation:

Through implementing minor random changes to individuals, mutation gives a way to humans to embark upon journeying in the space of solutions beyond the capabilities of parents. This would ensure that the genetic pool of the population is well represented and which in turn will prevent the populations from drifting towards solutions which are not as optimal.

G. Replacement:

In this new world, the frailest individuals in the population are washed away, and are supplanted by new offspring that arise through crossover and genetic mutation. Through this method which is continued on next generations, the play is getting evolved.

H. Termination:

Until a termination requirement is satisfied, the algorithm iterates through generations. This criterion could be reaching a predetermined performance level, convergent solutions, or a fixed number of generations given in the GA.

Fig 5. Flowchart of Genetic Algorithm

By utilizing evolutionary algorithms in the antenna design, a large solution space may be explored and new and optimized configurations that can greatly improve gain and other performance metrics can be found. The final size obtained after the implementation is 6.49 mm.

IV. ANTENNA DESIGN WITH NEW SLOT SIZE

A new antenna is constructed in order to generate the necessary results in the HFSS program when the genetic algorithm results are obtained. The only parameter size altered from the previous design and that is the length of the rectangular slot. All other parameter sizes, substrate's material and operating frequency are unchanged. The mentioned antenna with the top and bottom view for the improvised slot length are shown in Fig 6 and 7 respectively.

Fig 6. Antenna top view with the new slot size

Fig 7. Antenna bottom view with the new slot size

An array with two elements and an array with four elements is comparable to an array with a single element are reconstructed using new slot length which is obtained after implementing the genetic algorithm. This will help to enhance gain, bandwidth, and directivity for every antenna array design respectively. Fig 8 and 9 shows the two elements and the four elements suggested antenna array designs using new slot length.

Fig 8. Two elements antenna design with the new slot size

Fig 9. Four elements antenna design with the new slot size

V. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Before implementing GA in proposed antenna arrays:

Before implementing genetic algorithm, the following outcomes are achieved for antenna arrays consisting of single, two, and four elements in HFSS.

1) *Single element results:*

The figures – 10, 11, 12, and 13 displays the outcomes of the suggested antenna with circular patch and defective ground. Fig 10. Shows the S parameters of the proposed antenna, after simulating we obtained a bandwidth of 10.8GHz. The return loss obtained are -41.4626dB at 3.96GHz, -45.134dB at 7.4250GHz and -48.5684dB at 10.75GHz. Fig 11. Shows the recommended antenna's gain, and its highest value is 5.06dB. The suggested antenna's maximum directivity, as shown in Fig 12, is 5.43dB. Fig 13, shows the VSWR plot and we have obtained the value of 1.0170 at 3.96GHz, 1.0111 at 7.4250GHz and 1.0128 at 10.7850GHz.

Fig 10. S Parameter plot of the mentioned Antenna

Fig 11. Gain plot of the mentioned Antenna

Fig 12. Directivity plot of the mentioned Antenna

Fig 13. VSWR plot of the mentioned Antenna

2) *Two elements antenna array results:*

The outcomes of the suggested two – element array antenna positioned across from one another are displayed in the following figures – Fig 14, 15, 16, and 17.

Fig 14 displays the proposed two element array antenna’s S Parameters plot, after simulating we have obtained the bandwidth of 10.77GHz within the frequency range from 3.31GHz to 14.08GHz. Fig 15 displays the gain plot of the mentioned two – element array antenna, which has a 5.35dB maximum gain. The directivity plot of the mentioned two – element array antenna, with a maximum value of 5.77dB, is

shown in Fig 16. Fig 17, displays the mentioned two – element array antenna’s VSWR plot, from which we were able to get a value of 1.1989 at 7.985GHz.

Fig 14. S Parameter plot of the mentioned two - element array Antenna

Fig 15. Gain plot of the mentioned two - element array Antenna

Fig 16. Directivity plot of the mentioned two - elements Antenna array

Fig 17. VSWR plot of the mentioned two - element Antenna array

3) *Four elements antenna array results:*

The results of the suggested four – element antenna array which are placed orthogonal to each other are shown in the below figures – Fig 18, 19, 20, and 21.

Fig 18, displays the S Parameters plot of the suggested four elements array antenna, after simulation we have obtained the bandwidth of 10.86GHz. Fig 19, shows the gain plot of the suggested four elements array antenna and its maximum value obtained is 5.51dB. Fig 20, shows the directivity plot of the suggested four elements array antenna and its maximum value obtained is 6.10dB. Fig 21, displays the VSWR plot of the suggested four elements array antenna which is of 1.2329.

Fig 18. S Parameter plot of the mentioned four - element array Antenna

Fig 19. Gain plot of the mentioned four - element Antenna array

Fig 20. Directivity plot of the mentioned four - element Antenna array

Fig 21. VSWR plot of the mentioned four - element Antenna array

B. After implementing GA in proposed antenna arrays:

The following results obtained for single element, two – elements and four – elements array antenna, after implementing GA.

1) Single element antenna with improved slot size results:

The outcomes of the suggested antenna with new rectangular slot length on the circular patch are shown in the below figures – Fig 22, 23, 24, and 25.

Fig 22, displays the S Parameter of the proposed antenna with new slot size, after simulating the bandwidth obtained is 10.86GHz. The return loss obtained are -42.1230dB at 3.95GHz, -38.080dB at 7.4275GHz and -43.5628dB at 10.58GHz. Fig 23, showcases the plot of the gain of the suggested antenna with new slot size and its maximum value obtained is 5.11dB. Fig 24, demonstrates the suggested antenna with new slot size’s directivity, and its maximum value obtained is 5.45dB. Fig 25, displays the VSWR plot of the suggested antenna with new slot size, and we have obtained the values of 1.0326 at 3.95GHz, 1.0293 at 7.4275GHz and 1.0151 at 10.58GHz.

Fig 22. S Parameter plot of the mentioned antenna with the new slot size

Fig 23. Gain plot of the mentioned antenna with the new slot size

Fig 24. Directivity plot of the mentioned antenna with the new slot size

Fig 25. VSWR plot of the mentioned antenna with the new slot size

2) *Two elements array antenna with improved slot size results:*

The outcomes of the suggested two – elements array antenna with the revised slot size are displayed in the figures – Fig 26, 27, 28, and 29.

Fig 26, displays the S Parameter plot of the suggested two elements array antenna with new slot size, after simulation the obtained bandwidth is 10.93GHz within the frequency range from 3.31GHz to 14.24GHz. Fig 27, displays the gain plot of the suggested two elements array antenna with new slot size, its maximum value is 5.39dB. Fig 28, shows the directivity plot and its maximum value is 5.82dB. Fig 29, shows the VSWR plot of the recommended two elements array antenna having new slot size and its value is 1.1882 at 8.02GHz.

Fig 26. S Parameter plot of the mentioned two - element antenna array with the new slot size

Fig 27. Gain plot of the mentioned two - element antenna array with the new slot size

Fig 28. Directivity plot of the mentioned two - element antenna array with the new slot size

Fig 29. VSWR plot of the mentioned two - element antenna array with the new slot size

3) Four element array antenna with new slot size results:

The results of the suggested four elements array antenna with new slot size are shown in the following figures – Fig 30, 31, 32, and 33.

Fig 30, shows the S Parameter plot of the proposed four element antenna with new slot size, the obtained bandwidth is 10.99GHz. Fig 31, shows the gain plot of the suggested four elements array antenna with new slot size which has its maximum value as 5.53dB. Fig 32, shows the directivity plot of the suggested four elements array antenna with new slot size its maximum value after the simulation as 6.14dB. Fig 33, shows the VSWR plot of the four elements array antenna with new slot size having its value obtained as 1.1923 at 8.02GHz.

Fig 30. S Parameter plot of the mentioned four - element antenna array with the new slot size

Fig 31. Gain plot of the mentioned four - element antenna array with the new slot size

Fig 32. Directivity plot of the mentioned four - element antenna array with the new slot size

Fig 33. VSWR plot of the mentioned four - element antenna array with the new slot size

TABLE II.
COMPARISON OF RESULTS

	BEFORE GA RESULTS				AFTER GA RESULTS			
	BANDWIDTH (GHz)	GAIN (dB)	DIRECTIVITY (dB)	VSWR	BANDWIDTH (GHz)	GAIN (dB)	DIRECTIVITY (dB)	VSWR
SINGLE ELEMENT	10.80	5.06	5.43	1.0111	10.86	5.11	5.45	1.0160
TWO ELEMENT	10.77	5.35	5.77	1.1909	10.93	5.39	5.82	1.1882
FOUR ELEMENT	10.86	5.51	6.10	1.2329	10.99	5.53	6.14	1.1923

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on denim fabric, an ultra – wideband wearable conformal antenna is created. Antenna assures UWB characteristics. One of the key elements of the antenna design is the ability to achieve accurate matching of impedance throughout the Ultra – Wideband frequency spectrum, which is why a circular patch including a slot of rectangular shape in the central part, two elliptical slots, a rectangular microstrip feedline, and an interrupted ground construction are employed for this purpose. Similar to single element, two element and four element antenna array are designed.

The best suggested antenna is four element antenna array which displays a broad bandwidth of 10.86 GHz, occupying a frequency range of 3.22 – 14.08 GHz, and a peak gain of 5.51dB. The peak directivity of 6.10dB, and the value of Voltage Standing Wave Ratio (VSWR) is 1.2329.

Later, to be able to increase directivity, bandwidth, gain and other parameters of the antenna proposed, genetic algorithm is selected for optimization process. The same process is applied to two - elements antenna array and also four - elements antenna array. After implementing GA on four element antenna array, the improved bandwidth is 10.99 GHz, a peak gain and directivity values are 5.53dB and 6.14dB respectively. There is an improvement in gain, bandwidth, directivity, and other aspects of the characteristics of antenna in every possible designs discussed in this paper.

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